

Heterocyclic Fungicides. Part-I

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Twentysix 5-pyrazolone compounds have been tested for fungicidal activity against the fungus *Pyricularia Oryzae*, which causes the blast disease of rice plant. None of the above compounds contain either sulphur or halogens, which elements are invariably present in fungicides in use. Twentyfive of the twentysix chemicals tested in this investigation showed significant fungicidal activity. Certain correlations between structure and activity have been suggested.

EXTENSIVE work on the application of pyrazolone compounds in the manufacture of dyes and pharmaceuticals have been reported but relatively little work appears to have been done on the application of pyrazolones as fungicides. 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-amino-4, 4-dichloro-5-pyrazolone has been reported to show antibacterial and fungicidal activity¹. 1-(2, 3-Dichlorophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone and 2-(2-chlorophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone showed antifungal activity against the fungus *Corticium Saski*².

From this brief review it is seen that halogen is invariably present in all the compounds so far tested. So it was thought that if halogen free compounds of 5-pyrazolone be found to have fungicidal activity, then correlation between structure and activity may be found. A list of compounds prepared is given below in Tables 1A to 1E with the fungicidal activity noted against each.

TABLE 1(A)

Sl. no.	Name of the Compound	M.P. (°C)	Concentration in parts per million for inhibition of spore germination against <i>Pyricularia Oryzae</i>
1.	N-trichloromethyl-thiophthalimide (Commercial fungicide chemical called : ORTHOPHALTAN-WP. 50%)	—	100% inhibition at 1000 p.p.m.
2.	Ethyl acetoacetate	181 (B.P)	83.5% inhibition at 1000 p.p.m.
3.	Acetoacetanilide	85	82.5% inhibition at 1000 p.p.m.
4.	Nitroso-acetoacetanilide	89	66.5% inhibition at 1000 p.p.m.
5.	Antipyrin	113	91% inhibition at 1000 p.p.m.
6.	4-Nitroso-antipyrin	192	95% inhibition at 1000 p.p.m.
7.	4,4'-Aza-bis-(3-methyl-5-pyrazolone)	236(d)	100% inhibition at 5000 p.p.m.
8.	4,4'-Aza-Bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone)	181	100% inhibition at 500 p.p.m.

TABLE 1(B)

Sl. no.	2-Pyrazolin-5-ones				1(B)	Concentration in parts per million for inhibition of spore germination against <i>Pyricularia Oryzae</i>
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	M.P. (°C.)	
9.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	H	129	100% inhibition at 5000 ppm.
10.	CONH ₂	CH ₃	H	H	185	Ineffective
11.	H	CH ₃	H	H	226	81% inhibition at 1000 ppm.
12.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	NO	H	157	100% inhibition at 500 ppm.
13.	H	CH ₃	NO	H	231	100% inhibition at 5000 ppm.
14.	CONH ₂	CH ₃	NO	H	220	100% inhibition at 5000 ppm.
15.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	p-Hydroxy-mono-benzy-lidene		227	87.5% inhibition at 1000 ppm.

TABLE 1(C)

Sl. no.	(R ₁ ' & R ₁)	(R ₂ ' & R ₂)	(R ₃ & R ₃)	R ₄	M.P. (°C)	Concentration in parts per million for inhibition of spore germination against <i>Pyricularia Oryzae</i>
16.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₅	163	95% inhibition at 1000 ppm.
17.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₄ OH(p)	224	88% inhibition at 1000 ppm.
18.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (m)	193	86% inhibition at 1000 ppm.
19.	CONH ₂	CH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₅	204	96% inhibition at 500 ppm.

TABLE 1 (D)

Sl. no.	(R ₁ & R ₁)	(R ₂ & R ₂)	R ₃	M.P. (°C.)	Concentration in parts per million for inhibition of spore germination against <i>Pyricularia Oryzae</i>
20.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	203	98% inhibition at 1000 ppm,
21.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ OH(p)	215	90% inhibition at 1000 ppm.
22.	H	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ OH(p)	211	92.5% inhibition at 1000 ppm.
23.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (m)	224	80% inhibition at 1000 ppm.

TABLE 1 (E)

Sl. no.	(R ₁ & R ₁)	(R ₂ & R ₂)	R ₃	M.P. (°C.)	Concentration in parts per million for inhibition of spore germination against <i>Pyricularia Oryzae</i> .
24.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	165	100% inhibition at 1000 ppm.
25.	CONH ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	110	100% inhibition at 100 ppm.
26.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃		105	100% inhibition at 1000 ppm.

25 compounds containing either 5-pyrazolone nuclei or its precursors have some significant fungicidal activity against *Pyricularia Oryzae* except compound serial 10. A standard commercial fungicide chemical called ORTHOPHALTAN.WP.50% was tested under similar conditions and it was noted that the pyrazolone compounds had activity in the same range as the commercial fungicide. Compound serial 25, showed maximum activity, with 100% inhibition of the spores, at dilution of 100 parts per million. Compound serial 8, 12, 19, showed almost complete inhibition at a dilution 500 parts per million. The pyrazolones can be classed under five structural types, namely 4, 4'-aza-bis (5-pyrazolone), 2-pyrazolin-5 one with substituents in position 1, 3 and 4, 4,4'-bis (2-pyrazolin-5 one), 4,4'-bis-(2-pyrazolin 5 ol), cyclopropane derivative of 5-pyrazolone, structural type 1(E). Nitrosoacetoacetanilide was less active than acetoacetanilide but 4-nitroso-antipyrin was more active than anti pyrin, similarly 4-nitroso - 1 - phenyl -3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5 one was more active than 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one itself. 1-Acetamido-3-methyl compound serial 10, did not show any activity, though the corresponding compound serial 11, with hydrogen in place of the acetamido group had significant activity. It can be inferred from the significant activity of serial 9, and 11, that 2-pyrazolin-5 one nucleus itself is site for fungicidal property. Introduction of nitroso group in the four position enhances activity as can be seen from comparison of serial 9 and 12, 10 and 14. From Table 1(C), it was seen that compound 19 with acetamido group in one position shown maximum activity, so it is observed that the acetamido group in one position in the benzylidene-bis-compound is potent though the acetamido group in the mono-pyrazolone compound serial 10, was ineffective. Substitution of nitro-or hydroxyl group on the 4,4'-benzylidene phenyl group did not have any significant effect on the activity. The cyclopropane-spiro-pyrazolone compounds serial 24 to 26 indicate that the fused cyclopropane ring increases the activity. Comparison of the activities of the compounds serial 16 and 24 and serial 19 and 25 bringout the enhanced activity of the cyclopropane compounds.

Experimental

Preparation of compound, serial no. 1 : Orthophaltan WP. 50% is a commercial fungicide.

Preparation of compound, serial 2, 3, 5 and 9 : These were prepared by the known standard methods^{3,4}.

Preparation of Nitroso derivative of acetoacetanilide, serial 4 : Acetoacetanilide (2.5 g) was dissolved in minimum volume of glacial acetic acid. It was then kept in an ice bath for about 10 minutes, to bring the temperature of the solution to 10°C. Sodium nitrite (2g), solid, was added portion-wise to the solution. Yellow precipitate was obtained immediately but the reaction mixture was kept in the ice bath with stirring for 1 hr. It was then filtered and washed with dilute acetic acid and water. Product was recrystallised from (1:1) absolute alcohol, m.p. 89°, yield 3.0g.

Preparation of 4,4'-aza-bis-(3-methyl-5-pyrazolone), serial 7 : 3-Methyl-5-pyrazolone (2g.) and 3-methyl-4-nitroso-5-pyrazolone (2.6g.) were dissolved in minimum quantity of alcohol and refluxed for one hour. The solution was then concentrated and on cooling, yellow crystalline product separated out from the solution. It was filtered and recrystallised from (1:1) absolute alcohol, m.p. 236°(d), yield, 3.5g. The compound is highly soluble in water and it gives violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 45.59 ; H, 5.80 ; C₈H₁₂N₅O₂ requires C, 45.71 ; H, 5.71%).

Preparation of 4,4'-aza-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone), serial 8 : 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (2g) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-5-pyrazolone (2.32g) were dissolved in minimum amount of absolute alcohol, then fused sodium acetate was added to it and the mixture was refluxed for one hour. Alcohol was boiled off and the contents of the flask were added to water. It was kept over night, when needle shaped crystals came out of it, m.p. 181°, yield 3.7g.

Preparation of 1-amido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, serial 10 : Semicarbazone of ethylacetoacetate (5g) was dissolved in minimum ammoniacal methanol (1 ml of concentrated ammonia in 9 ml of methyl alcohol). It was allowed to stand for half an hour. The solution was evaporated at room temperature to a small volume and precipitate was filtered off. The residue was washed with a few drops of methanol, m.p. 185°, yield-3g.

Preparation of 3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, serial 11 : 4 ml. of hydrazine hydrate (50% solution) was taken in a beaker with ethyl ether (20 ml) and ethyl acetoacetate (8 ml) was added to it dropwise in order to avoid vigorous reaction. White crystalline solid separated out within one minute. It was then filtered, washed with ether, 3 to 4 times. On exposing to air, surface oxidation takes place and the compound becomes pink, m. p. 226°C, yield- 2.5g.

Preparation of 4-nitroso-5-pyrazolone compounds : serial 6, 12, 13, 14 : The different types of 5-pyrazolone (1g of each) were dissolved in minimum volume of (1:1) acetic acid in conical flasks. These were then kept in an ice bath for about 15 min, so that the temperature of the solutions were brought to 10°. Solid sodium nitrite (2g) was added in portions to each pyrazolone solution. Precipitates were obtained immediately but the reaction mixtures were kept in the ice bath with stirring for 1 hr. These were then filtered and washed with dilute acetic acid, followed by water. The products were recrystallised from (1:1) aqueous methyl alcohol, yield 80% to 60%.

TABLE 2

Sl.no. of the compound in table 1(A) and 1(B)	Molecular Formula	M.P. (°C.)	Yield (%)	Colour
6	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	192	80	Green
12	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂	157	75	Orange yellow
13	C ₄ H ₅ N ₃ O ₂	231	70	Yellow
14	C ₅ H ₆ N ₄ O ₃	220	60	Yellow

Preparation of mono-4 p-hydroxybenzylidene-5-pyrazolone, serial 15 : 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (2g) was dissolved in minimum amount of glacial acetic acid at room temperature. Then freshly distilled p-hydroxy benzaldehyde (1.2g) was added to this and left aside over night. Orange coloured crystals came out, filtered and washed with (1:1) acetic acid. The product was recrystallised from ethanol, m p. 227°, yield-2g.

preparation of 4,4'-aryl-bis-(2-pyrazolin-5-ones) Serial 16, 17, 18, 19 : 5-Pyrazolones (0.02 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of glacial acetic acid at room temperature. Then freshly distilled aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mole) were added and kept over night. Crystalline products were found to separate out

Preparation of pyrazolone-spiro-cyclopropane compounds, serial 24, 25, 26 : These were prepared from the corresponding benzylidene-4,4'-bis-heterocyclic precursor by similar methods :

The 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-heterocyclic compound carbonyl form, was dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10%). Solution of iodine in potassium iodide was added drop by drop to the above alkaline solution till no more precipitate separated out. The precipitate was filtered off and washed on the filter paper with solution of sulphurous acid, followed by water.

The analytical data of the compounds are given below :

TABLE 5

Sl. no. of the compounds in the Table 1(E)	Molecular formula	M.P. (°C.)	Yield %	Analysis			
				C	H	C	H
24	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	165	80	74.65	5.06	74.48	5.11
25	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄	110	75	55.43	4.34	55.61	4.30
26	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₈	105	70	70.75	4.71	70.59	4.68

of the solution by the addition of water dropwise to it. These were filtered, washed with acetic acid and melting points were determined. To the filtrate 10 ml of water was added, followed by 5 ml, of absolute alcohol. After few hours crystals came out of the solution and were filtered and washed with (1:1) acetic acid. These crystals were dissolved in minimum amount of 10% NaOH solution, as a result of which only bis-compounds become soluble and mono-compounds remain insoluble in the alkali. These were filtered in order to remove mono-derivatives and the residues were washed with water. Bis-compounds were collected from the filtrate by the addition of few ml. of hydrochloric acid.

TABLE 3

Sl no. of the compounds in the Table 1(C).	Molecular formula	M.P. (°C.)	Yield (%)	Colour
16	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂	163	60	Yellow
17	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃	224	65	Orange yellow
18	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₄	193	60	Yellowish white
19	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄	204	55	Pinkish brown

Preparation of 4,4'-aryl-bis-(2-pyrazolin-5-ols), serial 20, 21, 22, 23 : 5-Pyrazolones (0.02 mole) were dissolved in minimum amount of absolute alcohol at room temperature, To these solutions, freshly distilled aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mole) were added, followed by 20 drops of piperidine. These were allowed to stand when within 10 min crystalline solids separated out. These were filtered and washed 2 to 3 times with absolute alcohol to remove the coloured impurities. A portion of these were recrystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 4

Sl.no. of the compounds in Table 1(D)	Molecular formula	M.P. (°C)	Yield %	Colour
20	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂	203	55	White
21	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃	215	50	Brownish white
22	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃	211	50	Orange red
23	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₄	224	55	Brown

Procedure for preparation of stock solutions of the test compounds and the fungicidal assay : For the present work of fungicidal assay the standard method⁵ with slight modifications was used. The procedure consists of a dummy run to fix the range of dilution which is followed by a detailed study at different dilutions. Stock solution of the compounds serial 1 and 7 were prepared by dissolving the chemical (0.1g) in 10 ml of sterilised water. Stock solutions of compounds serial from 1 to 6 and from 9 to 23 were prepared by dissolving the chemicals (0.1g) in 1 ml 2N NaOH solution and diluting to 10 ml. with sterilised water. Stock solution of compound serial 8, was made by dissolving the compound (0.1g) in rectified spirit (1 ml) and then diluting to 10 ml. with sterilised water. Stock solution of compounds serial from 24 to 26, were made by dissolving the chemicals (0.1g) in 1 ml of acetone and diluting to 10 ml. with sterilised water. The data of fungicidal activity of the test chemicals against *Pyricularia Oryzae* is given in the table VI. With chemicals serial no. 8, and 24 the

TABLE 6

Sl.no. of compounds in Tables 1(A), 1(B), 1(C), 1(D), and 1(E).	Dilution in ppm.	Inhibition in test slide (%)	Inhibition in control slide (%)
1	62.5	85	2
	125	90.5	
	250	96.5	
	500	97.5	
	1000	100	
2	62.5	50	2
	125	74.5	
	250	77.5	
	500	80	
	1000	83.5	
3	62.5	39	0
	125	45.5	
	250	60.5	
	500	67.5	
	1000	82.5	

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4	62.5	54.5		19	250	29	
	125	66.5	10		500	96	6
	250	68.5			1000	100	
	500	82.5		20	62.5	45	
5	1000	90			125	70	0
	62.5	32.5			250	85	
	125	36.5	2		500	90	
	250	67.5			1000	98	
	500	76		21	62.5	35	
6	1000	91			125	62.5	2
	62.5	17.5			250	71	
	125	55	0		500	75.5	
	250	60			1000	90	
	500	69		22	62.5	34	
7	1000	95			125	50	
	500	25			250	71	2
	1000	31	8		500	82.5	
8	2500	100			1000	92.5	
	100	19		23	62.5	41	
	250	57	10		125	53	
9	500	100			250	60	5
	1000	16			500	77.5	
	2500	18	8		1000	80	
10	5000	100		24	250	18	
	62.5				500	60	8
	125	Ineffective	2		1000	100	
	250			25	25	11	
	500				50	87	5
11	1000				100	100	
	62.5	35		26	250	44	
	125	43.5	2		500	89	7
	250	66			1000	100	
	500	76					
12	1000	81					
	100	17					
	250	81	10				
13	500	100					
	1000	14					
	2500	51	6				
14	5000	100					
	1000	11					
	2500	47	7				
15	5000	100					
	62.5	47.5					
	125	61.0					
	250	66.5	5				
16	500	72.5					
	1000	87.5					
	62.5	35					
	125	40	0				
	250	75					
	500	85					
17	1000	95					
	62.5	49					
	125	65	2				
	250	70					
	500	82.5					
18	1000	88					
	62.5	51					
	125	57	5				
	250	61					
	500	76.5					
	1000	86					

spores which are germinated at and above 100 ppm had very short germ tubes. No phytotoxicity was shown by serial 1 and 8 on rice seedlings grown in trays of two blast-susceptible varieties of rice Ratna and Co-13.

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